

An improvement in the measure of recent geomorphic changes using digital photogrammetry

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Changes manifested in relief are principally due to the dynamics of either external or internal earth processes, climate change or human intervention.

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External processes are in continuous change however dynamics can be shown either, as a slow and progressive geomorphic change, or as significant landscape modifications. In short, geomorphic changes must be considered as modifications of slope geometry.

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Landslides are an excellent example of these geomorphic changes, because they represent an important contribution to denudation and relief evolution processes.

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Introduction:

• *It is therefore of interest to know to what extent present/recent (a few decades) slope instability processes are contributing to geomorphic mass transfer.*

Introduction:

• To know whether their activity shows changes that could be assigned to variations in the landslide triggering factors: seismic, tectonism, climate, and human activity (Palmquist and Bible, 1980).

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- To measure the importance of man as a relief modifying agent is one of the ideas that at present turns out to be more attractive in earth sciences, and to compare its role in geomorphic change with other external processes such as landslides.

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Introduction:

One possible approach, is to obtain detailed representations of land surface geometry at different time intervals. The magnitude of geometrical changes could provide means to quantify the contribution of landslides to “geomorphic” mass transfer.

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Introduction:

•Probably, aerial images are the source of information most widely used to analyse recent geomorphic changes because they have high potential to provide information about the landscapes depicted.

-Aerial digital photogrammetry enables one to obtain the semantic information contained in the images and the geometrical information about the slopes depicted.

•In developed areas it is possible to use images from flights corresponding to different years, some dating from before 1950, to analyse slope modifications into this period.

•The possibility to use the approach described depends on three factors:

- Accuracy of geometrical determinations
- Spatial coverage
- Time interval between successive measurements

It's not possible to have optimum conditions for these three factors, within reasonable economic limits.

Introduction:

BUT

Examples found in literature showing the use of this technique, despite producing highly accurate and precise digital elevation models, also contain problems, such as errors in the differences between the relative origins of each set of images.

Differentials measured as landslide displacements can be considered as real displacement or errors due to different data origins. To correct this type of error a proper measurement of the real displacement must be carried out.

The improvement of these measurements allows better precision in the absolute orientation of flights, and therefore, an increase in the accuracy of the real geomorphic change.

The data obtained for landslides compared with that obtained from the human intervention in the slopes, also shows the role of man in landscape change.

An aerial photograph of a rural landscape. A dirt road winds through the scene, connecting several buildings and fields. The terrain appears to be a mix of green grass and brownish soil, possibly indicating some erosion or displacement. There are several trees scattered throughout the area. The overall scene is a typical rural setting.

Others issues addressed:

Specific:

- Is model resolution good enough to observe terrain displacements?
- Can reliable measurements be performed?
- Which combination of data-acquisition and processing techniques provide the best quality model?

Case study:

This analysis is applied in the central part of the Magdalena-Pas Valley, in the Cantabrian Range, northern Spain. The area analysed covers 3 km².

The altitudes range are between 200 and 1,000 m. Annual rainfall is about 1,350 mm; events of 100 mm/day may occur with recurrence intervals of 2–5 years.

Case study:

From a geological point of view the area is a moderately folded and faulted terrain. The northern limit has a structure formed by Carboniferous limestones and Triassic sandstones thrusting southwards over a succession of Mesozoic materials that are dipping southwards. The bottom of this series is formed by Triassic (Keuper) marls, clays and evaporites combined with ophites, which appear in the core of diapiric folds, overlain by Jurassic marls, limestones, dolostones and sandy-silty-clayey Purbeck-Wealden Facies (González Díez, 1995)

Case study:

Slope movements affect roughly 25% of the area, mostly over the Keuper and saprolite, which covers ophites (González-Díez et al.,1996-1999). The typologies of landslides registered are mainly earth flows and earth slides on Keuper clay, with average size about 1,250 m².

Year	Scale	G.S.D. (m)	No. of Images	Contro/ch eck points used	Observations
2003	1:5,000	0.118	20	47	Negative, colour Photogrammetric scanner
1988	1:15,000	0.236	4	12/63	Negative, colour Photogrammetric scanner

The technique is being applied to the analysis of past and present landforms depicted in images belonging to two flights (1988 and 2003).

Results:

Models precision

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Results:

Error vector

Year	Relative orientation RMS (m)	Triangulation RMS (m)	Precisión 2003 $(Ro^2+Tr^2)^{0.5}$ (m)	Precisión 1988 $(P(x,y,z2003)^2 + C(e(x,y,z1988))^2 + Tr(x,y,z1988)^2)^{0.5}$	Geomorphic change (\bar{U}) $\bar{U} f(Px,Py,Pz)$ (m)
2003	X: ± 0.153 Y: ± 0.136 Z: ± 0.133	X: ± 0.034 Y: ± 0.043 Z: ± 0.081	X: ± 0.157 Y: ± 0.143 Z: ± 0.156		$\bar{U}_{XY} = \pm (EX^2 + EY^2)^{0.5} =$ $\bar{U}_{XY} = \pm 0.212$ $\bar{U}_{XYZ} = \pm (EX^2 + EY^2 + EZ^2)^{0.5}$ $\bar{U}_{XYZ} = \pm 0.263$
1988	X: ± 0.075 Y: ± 0.091 Z: ± 0.027	X: ± 0.146 Y: ± 0.162 Z: ± 0.282		X: ± 0.227 Y: ± 0.234 Z: ± 0.323	$\bar{U}_{XY} = \pm (EX^2 + EY^2)^{0.5} =$ $\bar{U}_{XY} = \pm 0.326$ $\bar{U}_{XYZ} = \pm (EX^2 + EY^2 + EZ^2)^{0.5}$ $\bar{U}_{XYZ} = \pm 0.459$

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Measuring landslides

Results: Analysis of slope evolution

In eleven areas (3, 5, 6, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 16 and 17), there is evidence of landslides activity either in 1988 or in 2003 but not in both periods simultaneously.

So, in these areas it is impossible to measure geomorphic changes between both dates.

Landslide processes were identified in seventeen areas and eight sub areas.

In six areas (1, 2, 4, 7, 8, 15) there is geomorphological evidence of continuous activity of landslide processes during the 15 year study period (1988-2003).

The activity affects only landslide crowns in two areas (2 and 4), whereas activity that affects crowns and deposits occurs in four more areas (1, 7, 8 and 16).

In some cases, it is possible to identify several crowns in each area.

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Results:

Crowns	Average length (dl) in western point (m)	Average real length (DL) in western point (m)	Average length (dl) in central point (m)	Average real length (DL) in central point (m)	Average length (dl) in Eastern point (m)	Average real length (DL) in eastern point (m)
1a	0,74	0,76	4,27	4,29	0,82	0,94
1b	0,4	0,77	2,79	2,97	0,43	0,45
4a	1,92	2,11	2,04	2,30	2,84	3
4b	0,88	0,99	0,67	0,87	2,35	2,64
4c	2,6	2,81	2,81	3,13	1,74	1,87
4d	1,18	1,38	2,39	2,86	1,4	1,49
4f1	2,58	2,64	2,84	3,35	1,42	1,71
4f2	0,12	0,13	0,75	1,32	0,37	1,05
7	0	0	0,71	1,75	1,22	2,42
8a	2,68	2,81	3,75	4,31	0,78	1,47
8b	3,65	4,25	0,72	1,02	2,31	3,08
8c	0	0	0,87	1,26	0,51	0,62
8d	0,88	2,11	0	1	0	0
8e	1,23	2,49	3,92	4,14	1,69	1,71

Average length (m)= 1.55 ± 0.33 m Average real length= 1.91 ± 0.46 m

The average length of the displacements, *in planimetry*, measured between crowns identified in the images from 1988 and 2003 is 1.5 ± 0.33 m, the backward movement of the crowns over 15 years give a rate of 10 cm/year.

The real upward movement of crowns in 15 years is 1.9 ± 0.46 m. This displacement supposes a rate of 13 cm/year.

Results:

Green: Landslides indentified in the images from 2003

ID	POLIGON	AREA (ha)	Average thickness (m)	CRONO. GROUP	VOLUME (m3)
				12	
58	567	0,0001614	0,086736175	12	0,351
46	488	0,0007127	0,132368694	12	0,943
14	368	0,0108434	0,921339424	12	7,771
7	351	0,0009752	0,216598085	12	2,112
36	418	0,0010517	0,538133402	12	5,660
62	723	0,001251	0,082415368	12	1,031
71	741	0,0013245	0,261039476	12	3,457
52	516	0,0013609	0,297283761	12	4,046
32	403	0,0013882	0,262575832	12	3,645
59	694	0,0014405	0,261187774	12	3,762
44	486	0,0015474	0,413755971	12	6,402
5	347	0,0016204	0,164901626	12	2,672
6	350	0,0018135	0,089585023	12	1,625
51	514	0,0020265	0,39578859	12	8,021

Results: Analysis of slope evolution

Orange: Landslides indentified in the images from 1988

Landslide group	Chronological group	Total no. of movements	Area affected by landslides (m ²)	Volume of movements (m ³)
12	Pre2003-post1988	72	11,871.97 ± 0.2	5,645.015±0.26
11	Pre1988-post1965	10	22,000.00 ± 0.2	34,970.610±0.26
Totals		82	33,871.97 ± 0.2	40,615.625±0.26

ID	POLIGON	AREA (ha)	Average thickness (m)	CRONO. GROUP	VOLUME (m3)
12	525	0,005	1,7305	11	87,769
4	304	0,006	0,6452	11	41,166
10	523	0,008	0,7036	11	52,903
6	307	0,008	0,7835	11	66,198
5	305	0,009	0,7971	11	68,569
19	677	0,010	2,6663	11	267,230
3	303	0,012	1,7429	11	203,998
13	526	0,015	0,3999	11	58,228
18	545	0,026	1,1742	11	299,615
11	524	0,041	1,1734	11	481,636
14	529	0,046	1,63	11	745,724
2	301	0,073	0,7527	11	546,046

Results:

Area, volumes, mobilization and denudation rates of the landslide chronological groups identified in the case study. Top table: González et al. (1996 and 1999);

Surface of Villafufre: 524.552 ha. This study was done in 1994

Landslide group	Chronological group	Total no. of movements	Area affected by landslides (ha)	Volume of movements (m ³)	% of the area affected by landslides	% of the case study area	Area rate ha/year	Volume rate m ³ /año	Rate mm/year
1	<25	18	11.88	45840	1.035	2.30	0.475	1833.60	0.350
2	25-200	20	42.38	87236	14.503	8.10	0.242	498.49	0.095
3	200-3.000 B.P.	11	14.12	22768	4.832	2.70	0.005	8.13	0.002
4	3000 B.P.-5000 B.P.	4	15.84	259535	5.421	3.02	0.008	129.77	0.025
5	5.000 B.P.-5500 B.P.	1	3.20	25600	1.095	0.61	0.006	51.20	0.010
6	5500 B.P.-15000 B.P.	0	0.00	0	0.000	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.000
7	15000 B.P.-30000 B.P.	1	4.80	480000	1.643	0.92	0.000	33.10	0.006
8	30000 B.P.-50000 B.P.	0	0.00	0	0.000	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.000
9	50000 B.P.-120000 B.P.	0	0.00	0	0.000	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.000
10	>120000 B.P.	1	200.00	143200000	68.442	38.13	?	?	?
Totals		56	292.22	144120980	100.000	55.71			

Landslide group	Chronological group	Total no. of movements	Area affected by landslides (m ²)	Volume of movements (m ³)	% of the area Affected by landslides	% of the case study area	Area rate ha/year	Volume rate m ³ /año	Rate mm/year
12	post1988-pre2003	72	11871.97 ± 0.2	5645.015±0.26	0.41	0.2	0.079	376.33	0.072
11	pre1988-post1965	19	22000.00 ± 0.2	34970.610±0.26	0.75	0.4	0.088	1398.82	0.267
Totals		91	33871.97 ± 0.2	40615.625±0.26	1.16	0.6	0.167	1775.16	0.194

Results:

Landslide rates

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Triggering factors
and slope
evolution

Results: Triggering factors

December 2002

December 2003

In 1983 a cyclonic rainfall event had rainfall rates over 100mm in 24 hours during 2-4 days, producing plenty landslides in Cantabria. Subsequently, other cyclonic rainfall events have been linked with landslide reactivations. The figure shows the total amounts of accumulated rainfall (mm) and rain rates (mm/hour) in 2002 and 2003. The red circle shows the landslide events registered in the area- these events are related to intense rainfalls.

Rainfall with intensities over 150 mm in 24 hour do not generate landslides. However, rainfall with rain rates between 50 and 60 mm in 24 hours, generates landslides, if the rainfall event continues during 3 or 4 days with the same intensity.

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Man role

Results: man contribution to slope evolution

The geomorphic changes due to human interventions supposes a volume changes bigger than $14,743 \text{ m}^3$.

Conclusions:

- The methodology presented allows measurement of landslide displacements bigger than 0.33 cm (planimetry) and 0.46 cm (3D) between images from a 15 year period. This displacement is coherent with measurements carried out on buildings that appear in both sets of images.

- The resolution of the model is good enough to observe and measure terrain displacements. The backward movement of the crowns over 15 years give a rate of 10 cm/year. The real upward movement of crowns suppose a rate of 13 cm/year.

- Landslide processes were identified in seventeen unstable areas and eight sub areas. In six areas there is geomorphological evidence of continuous activity of landslide processes, which affects landslide crowns and deposits. In eleven areas there is evidence of landslide activity either in 1988 or in 2003 but not in both periods simultaneously.

72 landslides (earth flow, earth slides, flows) were identified from 1988 to 2003, these features affect a surface of 11,872 m² and a volume of 5,645 m³.

An aerial photograph of a rural landscape. In the upper left, there is a small wooden building with a dark roof. In the upper right, a larger farm building with a brown roof is visible, with a white car parked nearby. The central and lower portions of the image show a large, open field with a herd of sheep scattered across it. The terrain appears to be a mix of green grass and brownish soil, possibly indicating erosion or denudation. A large, semi-transparent watermark reading "Copyright © authors" is oriented diagonally across the center of the image.

Conclusions:

- Denudation rates measured from 30,000 years B.P. to present are increasing with time. An increase of one order of magnitude has been registered between 1770 to 1965 (0.096 mm/year) and from 1965 to 1988 (0.26 mm/year). An decrease of one order of magnitude has been registered between 1988 to 2003 (0.072 mm/year).
- The landscape change generated by human activities, between 1988 to present, is 2.6 times bigger than the volume generated by landslides. Human activities represent a denudation rate of 0.187 mm/year, very similar to landslides rates identified between 1965 to 1988.

Thank you

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Results:

Orthoimage from 2003 project

Orthoimage from 1988 project

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Results:

Determining the differences in the origin of both projects

Differences between the origins of images belonging to 1988 and 2003

Displacement
RMS (m)

dX	dy	dz
0.3110	0.3376	0.7621

Results:

variable	Western point distance (m)	Central point distance (m)	Eastern point distance (m)
Height difference, dh	0.14	0.45	0.46
Length difference (projection), dl	0.74	4.27	0.82
slope in %	18.55	10.63	55.69
Real length, DL	0.76	4.29	0.94

Results:

Black: Landslides indentified by González Díez et al. (1996;1999)

Pink: Areas with identified landslide processes

Orange: Landslides indentified in the images from 1988

Green: Landslides indentified in the images from 2003

Results:

Examples

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Results: premonitory features

1988

Image analysis allows identification of premonitory cracks, but with limitations due to image quality.

Newer photos provide much better resolution, but it is difficult to assess imminent ruptures.

2003

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Results: slope evolution

Land instability migrates upwards so crowns move to the upper parts of slopes

Methodology

Flight design

Cessna 402

Navigation Systems

GPS, VOR, ADF,
RMI, HSI.

Escala de vuelo: 1/5.000
 Rec. Longitudinal: 60%
 Rec. Transversal: 30%
 Nº de Pasadas: 2
 Nº de Fotografías: 22
 Avion : CESSNA 402
 Elipsoide Hayford
 Proyeccion : U.T.M.
 Huso : 30

Apolonio Moraes, 6 Bajo 28036 Madrid Tlfo. 91 443 02 86 Fax 91 457 82 86 www.hifsa.com

GRAFICO DE VUELO

ZONA: VILLAFUFRE
 PROVINCIA: CANTABRIA
 H.M.N. 50.000: 58;59
 CLIENTE: UNIVERSIDAD DE CANTABRIA
 CAMARA: RMK TOP 15
 PELICULA: KODAK 2444
 FECHA DE VUELO: 05/08/05
 FOCAL: 153,324 mm
 O.T.: 2005/5235
 ESCALA GRAFICO: 1/50.000

Methodology

Colour analogical images were taken by a RMK TOP 15 (153,324 mm) Camera (KODAK Aerocolor III 2444) during the flight.

Flight plan name: VILLAFUFRE5000

Run number: 1

Run attempt no: 1 Date: 05/08/2005

- 3257 E [30] 428754 N 4790808 14:05:12.3
- 3258 E [30] 428354 N 4790810 14:05:17.2
- 3259 E [30] 427950 N 4790819 14:05:22.1
- 3260 E [30] 427550 N 4790825 14:05:26.9
- 3261 E [30] 427148 N 4790829 14:05:31.7
- 3262 E [30] 426746 N 4790836 14:05:36.6
- 3263 E [30] 426342 N 4790841 14:05:41.5
- 3264 E [30] 425938 N 4790840 14:05:46.4
- 3265 E [30] 425534 N 4790843 14:05:51.2
- 3266 E [30] 425134 N 4790847 14:05:55.9
- 3267 E [30] 424734 N 4790853 14:06:00.7

Run number: 2

Run attempt no: 1 Date: 05/08/2005

- 3246 E [30] 424714 N 4790048 14:02:37.7
- 3247 E [30] 425130 N 4790046 14:02:42.7
- 3248 E [30] 425534 N 4790039 14:02:47.6
- 3249 E [30] 425938 N 4790031 14:02:52.4
- 3250 E [30] 426340 N 4790029 14:02:57.2
- 3251 E [30] 426742 N 4790025 14:03:02.0
- 3252 E [30] 427146 N 4790018 14:03:06.8
- 3253 E [30] 427548 N 4790016 14:03:11.6
- 3254 E [30] 427950 N 4790011 14:03:16.4
- 3255 E [30] 428354 N 4790007 14:03:21.2
- 3256 E [30] 428756 N 4790005 14:03:26.0

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Methodology

DEUTSCHER KALIBRIERDIENST DKD
 Kalibrierlaborium für geometrische Optik
 Calibration laboratory for measured quantities geometric optics
 Akkreditiert durch die / accredited by the
 Akkreditierungsstelle des DKD bei der
PHYSIKALISCH-TECHNISCHEN BUNDESANSTALT (PTB)

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9123
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 04-11

Kalibrierschein
 Calibration Certificate

Gegenstand
 Object: Aerial Survey Camera

Hersteller
 Manufacturer: Carl Zeiss D-73446 Oberkochen

Typ
 Type: RMK TOP 15

Fabrikat/Serien-Nr.
 Serial number: 142 834

Auftraggeber
 Customer: Hell Henke Fotogrammetria S.L. Alberto Alcoer, 39 Bajo DCHA E-28016 Madrid Spain

Auftragsnummer
 Order No.: 41.403

Anzahl der Seiten des Kalibrierscheins
 Number of pages of the certificate: 4

Datum der Kalibrierung
 Date of calibration: 30.11.04

Datum
 Date: 01.12.04

Unterschrift
 Signature: Dr. Wiedemann, Müller

Carl Zeiss
 Industrielle Messtechnik GmbH
 Mess- und Kalibrierzentrum
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 Unterschrift Datum Unterschrift Datum
 Head of the calibration laboratory Person in charge

Seite 2

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 04-11

Camera type: RMK TOP 15 SERIAL NO. 142834
 LENS TYPE: PLEOCCN A3 SERIAL NO. 444137
 MAX. APERTURE: F/4 NOM. FOCAL LENGTH: 153 MM

1) CALIBRATED FOCAL LENGTH = 153.324 MM

2) DISTORTION / Ø. Ø01 MM, REFERRING TO P.P. OF SYMMETRY PPS

S/MM:	0	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100	110	120	130	140	150
5	0	-1	-1	-2	-3	-2	-2	-1	-1	-2	0	1	1	0	1	0
6	0	-2	-2	-3	-4	-3	-3	-3	-1	-1	-1	0	1	1	0	0
7	0	-2	-2	-3	-3	-2	-2	-1	-2	-1	-1	0	2	3	5	3
8	0	-1	-2	-3	-3	-2	-1	-1	-1	-1	0	1	2	3	4	2

AV. Ø -1 -2 -3 -3 -2 -2 -2 -1 -1 -1 0 1 2 3 4 1

3) P.P. OF AUTOCOLLIMATION AND FIDUCIAL CENTRE, REFERRING TO PPS

P.P. OF AUTOCOLLIMATION PPA X= -0.004 YL 0.009 MM
 FIDUCIAL CENTRE FC X= -0.014 Y= -0.007 MM
 CORNER FIDUCIAL CENTRE FCC X= -0.016 Y= -0.009 MM

4) FIDUCIAL MARKS, REFERRING TO PPS

X1= 112.995 X2= 113.015 X3= -0.016 X4= 3.011 MM
 Y1= -0.008 Y2= -0.005 Y3= 112.988 Y4= 112.918 MM
 DISTANCE 1-2= 226.010 3-4= 2" 1. 4" 1.
 X5= 112.992 X6= 113.012 X7= 113.015 X8= 112.986 MM
 Y5= 113.004 Y6= 113.017 Y7= 112.991 Y8= -3.015 . 1

5) PHOTOGRAPHIC RESOLUTION POWER, IN CYCLES PER MM (AS PER DEFINITION, R. P. IS NOT A CAL. ITEM) AREA WEIGHTED AVERAGE RESOLUTION 93

FIELD ANGLE / DEG = 0 7 14 21 28 35 42

RESOL. LINES 130 129 126 126 118 118 96
 TANGENTIAL LINES 130 102 F. 3. 3b -of 72

FILM: KODAK PANATOP 34 x SPEED 40 AFS
 DEVELOPED IN NIPA 74 C FVL 11 T

6) Filter

7) Magnifies

8) Measuring uncertainty
 Distortion: U = 3 µm; Point of symmetry and collimation: U = 3 µm; Image center: U = 5 µm; Camera constant: U = 5 µm
 The specification indicates the upgraded measuring uncertainty resulting from the multiplication of the standard measuring uncertainty by the factor k = 2. It was determined in conformity with DKD-3. The values of the measurement parameter lie within the specified range with a probability of 95%.

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RMK TOP 15 NO. 142834

PHOTOGRAPHIC RESOLUTION POWER

AV. 93 CYCLES MM (230 MM NEGATIVE SIZE)

DEPARTURE OF AVERAGE DISTORTION FROM ZERO REFERENCE

PRINCIPAL POINT (PPA), PPS) AND FIDUCIAL CENTRE (FC)

COORDINATES, REFERRING TO PPS

	X / MM	Y / MM
PPA	-0.004	0.009
FC	-0.014	-0.007
FCC (CORNER FIDUCIAL CENTRE)	-0.016	-0.009

± 0.01 MM. X-AXIS IS DEFINED BY FIDUCIAL MARK COORDINATES

Seite 3

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RMK TOP 15 NO. 142834
 PLEOCCN A3 4/153 NO. 444137
 CFL = 153.324 MM

DISTORTION / Ø. Ø01 MM, REFERRING TO PPS

Images from 2003 flight

(Vexcel 5,000). 15 μm

Photogrammetric workstation

- Internal orientation
- Relative orientation
- Absolute orientation

(Socet.Set with Orima and LPS photogrammetric softwares)

$$x = -f \frac{m_{11}(X - X_0) + m_{12}(Y - Y_0) + m_{13}(Z - Z_0)}{m_{31}(X - X_0) + m_{32}(Y - Y_0) + m_{33}(Z - Z_0)}$$

$$y = -f \frac{m_{21}(X - X_0) + m_{22}(Y - Y_0) + m_{23}(Z - Z_0)}{m_{31}(X - X_0) + m_{32}(Y - Y_0) + m_{33}(Z - Z_0)}$$

m_{ij} = function of ω, ϕ, κ (elements of rotation matrix)

(Kernsten y Haering, 1997)
Automatic internal orientation

(Kernsten y Haering, 1997)

Absolute orientation

Relative orientation

Methodology

Fieldwork starts with the construction a net of ground points made up of 47 points measured by double frequency GPS (Leica, System 500). One receiver served as base station, while the other was used as mobile receiver. All the points were supported by a GPS station of the European Terrestrial Reference System 1989 (ETRS89). The coordinates for the rest of the ground points were obtained for post-processing using the SKI-Pro software (Leica-Geosystems). Finally coordinates for all the ground points were transformed to UTM ED50.

Measuring in RTK

Static mode

Methodology

A regular grid-base DEM (pixel size of 1 m x 1 m) was obtained using the later photogrammetric software.

This DEM was checked with either new points taken in the field by the GPS in cinematic mode, or with low resolution DEMs. Points with low C.F. were discarded. (Ackermann, 1996; Cory y McGill, 1999).

Cinematic mode

A seed DEM was created with the remaining points. With this seed model a new TIN-base DEM (pixel size of 0.10 m x 0.10 m) was calculated applying an adaptive strategy. The model was based on a map of break lines that represent the main rupture lines of the topography. Those lines represent the limits of crowns, levees, etc. Each point was checked using the stereoscopic tools in the Digital Photogrammetric Workstation (DPW). The blunder points located were edited by and re-measured using the DPW re-measured tools.